

EMPIRE, SCIENCE AND GEOMETRY AT THE ORIGINS OF EARLY MODERN ARCHITECTURE

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Abstract: *This article explores the inceptions of architectural science. Camillo Guarino Guarini, the celebrated author of sundry kaleidoscopic symmetries, is the first one to utter an explicit written colligation between Mathematics and Magic on one side and Light and Architecture on the other. Pellegrino Tibaldi, together with the Jesuit builders of El Escorial, the monumental Palace cum Basilica of Spanish Emperor Phillip the Second, enshrined a set of enigmas for the future regarding the issue that only we have recently begun to disclose. In the Eastern Empire of China, which still calls itself the Empire of the Centre, similar questions were poised through Daoist numerology and geomancy, evoking the perennial symmetry of nature. Eventually a fusion of horizons was attained in the miraculous architectural oeuvre of Giuseppe Castiglione or, more properly, Lang Shining (郎世宁), a third Northern Italian and arguably the last grand Chinese painter. In a collection of frescoes once exposed at his own building, the cathedral of Nantang in Beijing and later at the Juanqinzhai (卷勤斋), the retirement palace of Emperor Qianlong in the Forbidden City, it is possible to descry a mellow reconciliation between natural life and abstract geometry by virtue of focal perspective.*

Keywords: architectural composition, theory of architecture, Modernism, architectural symbolism, Oriental studies

1 THE FRESCOES IN THE LIBRARY OF EL ESCORIAL

In his treatise *Euclides Adauctus et Methodicus*, the sublime architect and priest Camillo Guarino Guarini (1671, p. 114) wrote the following in praise of the Savoyard King: “since the magic of insuperable wondrous mathematics shines brightly on marvellous and truly regal Architecture.”¹ It was not the first time in the history of Western thinking that the term *thaumaturga* that is, magic in Greek, applied to science or mathematics. For instance, some years before, Jean François Nicéron (Derrida, 1978), in the wake of Descartes, had written his *Thaumaturgus Opticus* or the *Magic of Optics* (a book on geometry of 1638).

Figure 1: The fresco of King Philip the Second in the library of El Escorial, Madrid (Biblioteca Real del Monasterio de San Lorenzo de El Escorial) by Miguel Ángel and Pellegrino Tibaldi.

However, it is the first time that the mathematics of “magic” are linked to kingly excellence in architecture, albeit Guarini was referring mainly to the superb palaces and gardens of Venaria Reale in Turin. In contemporary and 20th century architecture, the notion is quite the opposite; both schools of architecture and respected masters of the

¹ „Sed insuper *Thaumaturga Mathematicorum miraculorum insigni, vereque regali architectura coruscant: tallem etenim illam plaudenti conclamat aspectu venaria amaenis instructa viridariis substructionibusque superbis turrata regius voluptatum, deliciarumque thronus, augustissima palatia, aedes sumptuosissima, aditus triumphalis magnarum urbium, aliaque permulta sua admirabili protoplastice ex cogitata et ad artem ultimam solis nutibes, aspectuque directa.*”

which *yīn* and *yáng* are intertwined to produce the world, the place where the faithful is situated in his meditation and the warlock in his ritual, from whence they can communicate with heaven as well as with earth (Robinet, 1999).

Number 3 emerges from the combination of the centre with the *yīn-yáng* duality. Similarly, the number 5 derives from addition of the centre to the four cardinal orientations, constituting a “pure” number that represents the natural order. Likewise, the number nine forms itself by combining the eight orientations of the *bāguà* with the centre. Therefore, 9 is considered the most relevant number on earth. From this number, geometric representations generate to reflect the earthly order and apply to architectural patterns. There is even a cosmological representation of all the former at the reverse of a mirror dating from Tang epoch (Fig. 10).

3.2 Parallelism between heavenly and earthly orders: *Xiāntiān Bāguà* and *Hòutiān Bāguà*

It is possible to obtain a three-dimensional model by virtue of a link between the heavenly and earthly orders, with a central axis occupied by the ruler of heaven and his son on earth (the emperor). In the *Yijing*, this model receives the following description:

古者包犧氏之王天下也，仰則觀象於天，俯則觀法於地。

“In ancient times, when *Bāoxī shì* (包犧) came to rule everything beneath the heaven, he looked around and contemplated the forms displayed in the heavens (the constellations), and looked down to contemplate the processes that were taking place on earth.”

Thus, we could establish a cosmological pattern in which heaven and earth are related. In this regard, the *Yijing* comments that:

在天成象，在地成形，变化见矣。

“In the heavens phenomena take form, on earth forms are configured. Thus change and transformation are manifested.”

Furthermore, heaven divides into four regions, each containing seven star formations. Mythical animals represent in this manner the four quadrants: turquoise dragon (east), vermilion phoenix (south), white tiger (west) and the mysterious dark war between a serpent and a turtle (north) (Fig. 11). These regions have a correlation on earth, both with

natural and human structures. This parallelism between heaven and earth is associated with *fēngshuǐ* (風水), which represents the traditional way to establish a cosmic structure for architectural design. Therefore, the Anterior-Heaven, which depicts the heavenly order, has a reflection on earth. As a result, from the Posterior-Heaven emerged trigrams organized in a different way to represent the earthly order.

Figure 11: The *Xuan Wu* (玄武) or mysterious war between a Serpent (the sun path) and a Turtle, which represents the earth, from this ancient picture both the number 8 and the well-known symbol for infinite ∞ that is, the Möbius strip, derive. Such an infinity concept is the basis for calculus.

Figure 12 shows the correlation between the Anterior-Heaven (celestial order) and Posterior-Heaven (earthly order) *bāguà* diagrams, which in turn lead to the *Hétú* and *Luòshū*. The parallelism between heaven and earth translates into a numerical correlation for different orientations. These cosmological diagrams apply to architectural design by means of the *fēngshuǐ* to attain harmony between humans and nature.

The multiplication process from two to four and then to eight is the result of adding a *yīn-yáng* duality to the previous modules. In a higher level of organization, 64 hexagrams are generated from 8 trigrams as basic modules of combinatory in pairs: the *Yījīng* uses the resulting hexagrams for divination purposes (Wilhelm and Baynes, 1960). In this regard, the term *shù* (数), used in China to refer to mathematics, justly means both calculation and destiny. This is similar to the evolution of mathematics in other parts of the world, as we have previously demonstrated.